

НОО ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНАЯ НАУКА

**ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ И
ПРИКЛАДНЫЕ
ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ:
ДОСТИЖЕНИЯ, ПРОБЛЕМЫ
И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ
РАЗВИТИЯ**

Сборник научных трудов по материалам
Международной научно-практической конференции

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ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНАЯ НАУКА**

**Теоретические и прикладные исследования:
достижения, проблемы и перспективы развития**

**Сборник научных трудов
по материалам Международной научно-практической конференции**

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Larin S., Lazareva L., Larina T. Analysis of branch peculiarities of social notions users about digital economics' products

Анализ отраслевых особенностей социальных представлений пользователей о продуктах цифровой экономики

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Abstract. Digitalization of all areas of human activity opens up new opportunities for entrepreneurship and brings tangible benefits to all consumers of digital economy products. At the same time, the development of the information system will lead to an aggravation of competition in the markets, will change the requirements for professional competencies of specialists, will lead to job cuts in many sectors of the economy. In this study, the authors substantiate the relevance of the development of the digital economy in modern conditions. The article presents the characteristics of global shifts in the world economy under the influence of the development of the digital economy. The analysis of the features of social representations of users about the products of the digital economy in a number of industries and in the labor market is carried out. It is concluded that the most significant benefits from using the products of the digital economy will be received by enterprises with a high level of human capital. It is established that digitalization will have a significant impact on the social perceptions of users about the products of the digital economy in all spheres of production.

Keywords: digitalization, products of digital economics, social perceptions of users, economic preferences.

Аннотация. Цифровизация всех областей жизнедеятельности человека открывает новые возможности для предпринимательства и приносит осязаемые преимущества всем потребителям продуктов цифровой экономики. Вместе с тем, развитие информационного уклада повлечет за собой обострение конкурентной борьбы на рынках, изменит требования к профессиональным компетенциям специалистов, приведет к сокращению рабочих мест в многих секторах экономики. В данном исследовании авторами обоснована актуальность развития цифровой экономики в современных условиях. Представлена характеристика глобальных сдвигов

в мировой экономике под влиянием развития цифровой экономики. Проведен анализ особенностей социальных представлений пользователей о продуктах цифровой экономики в ряде отраслей и на рынке труда. Сделан вывод о том, что наиболее значимые преимущества от использования продуктов цифровой экономики получают предприятия с высоким уровнем человеческого капитала. Установлено, что цифровизация окажет значительное влияние на социальные представления пользователей о продуктах цифровой экономики во всех сферах производства.

Ключевые слова: цифровизация, продукты цифровой экономики, социальные представления пользователей, экономические преимущества.

Introduction

Throughout history, the development of the economy has been based on inventions and innovative technological breakthroughs. Currently, the global Internet is considered to be such a breakthrough. It allows you to share a wide range of different software applications and stimulates the development of the economy in developed and developing countries. The development of the Internet has launched the mechanism of digitalization of the economy. In turn, the digital economy is rapidly transforming business and all areas of production. These transformations will lead to the formation of a new information and technological structure in the world economy.

Materials and methods

Conceptually, the interaction of users with Internet resources can be represented in the form of three mutually overlapping arrays of information or "clouds": clouds of resources for storing and processing information; clouds of connections for transmitting information; a cloud for creating networks, supporting relationships and developing cooperation. These clouds form the infrastructure of the digital economy, allow you to create new markets, provide channels for the transfer of information, the movement of resources and the regulation of market demand. It allows individual enterprises and individuals around the world to participate in the development of innovative products and technologies, increase their wealth, and simplify interaction among themselves. Moreover, this process is happening simultaneously all over the world.

Results and Discussion

1. Trends of development of digital economics

The development of the digital economy has become the driving force of the economic growth in recent years and is transforming society as a whole. The digital economy goes far beyond digitalization, information and automation of its processing. The digital economy paradigm is based on the use of a variety of innovative technologies and platforms. They include: the Internet of Things, the development of cloud computing, business analytics, wireless networks, mobile devices, social networks and much more. The digital economy uses these technologies to process traditional and large amounts of information.

The digital economy is based on computer networks, such as the Internet. The infrastructure of the digital economy supports the use of computer networks through: computer equipment; software; telecommunications equipment; services for information transmission;

network and / or wireless channels; information processing centers; the Internet of Things; services to support the functioning of the infrastructure of the digital economy [1]. It follows from this that the digital economy should be understood as a worldwide network of economic activities, commercial transactions and professional interactions, which are provided by information and communication technologies and the corresponding infrastructure.

The rapid development of the digital economy has led to six global shifts in the world economy [2]. Below is a brief description of them.

1. The Internet and its applications have largely changed the characteristic features of the functioning of global markets. This shift is taking place in both developed and developing countries. It is based on mobility, cloud computing, business analytics and social media resources.

2. Digitalization covers more and more industries in the global economy. It contributes to the growth of competition and the transformation of many sectors of the economy.

3. There is a change in the digital differences. Rich companies invest in innovative technologies in order to stay ahead of their competitors. Therefore, when conducting a policy of entering new markets, technology firms in developing countries face the need to solve new problems in the face of increasing competition.

4. The central place in the development of the digital economy is occupied by economic entities in emerging markets. Enterprises that are able to adapt their needs to the demands of the market will ensure rapid economic growth.

5. The introduction of innovative technologies has significantly increased the rate of all operations, from product development to its implementation. Therefore, business analytics and intellectual analysis are more in demand than ever to justify decisions made and minimize risks.

6. In the digital economy, many companies and enterprises are moving away from strict hierarchical structures and prefer the network structure as more market-oriented and organic.

Already today, these shifts have a significant impact on many enterprises.

2. Products of digital economics

Expanding access to products and technologies of the digital economy brings potential users the freedom to choose those that have the most convenient functional characteristics. Due to the introduction of innovations, greater social integration and increased efficiency, new, previously non-existent opportunities are opening up for users of digital economy products.

The products of the digital economy include, first of all, the Internet and related mobile devices and computer equipment, other means of collecting, storing, analyzing and exchanging information in digital form. The products of the digital economy include various digital payment systems and devices for making payments and other transactions, devices and equipment for electronic commerce and business process outsourcing, video communication tools, digital

identity identification systems and a fairly wide range of mobile equipment and devices. All of them, to one degree or another, provide potential users with new opportunities for the rapid implementation of a large number of everyday life options or various production operations, the implementation of which previously was associated with significant time costs and a number of other inconveniences. In addition, users of digital economy products have received a number of social advantages, which are expressed in the simplicity and convenience of communication and obtaining information, the emergence of new forms of leisure in the form of social networks, thanks to which the perception of deep social relationships and global community is gradually developing in the minds of users.

For a better understanding of social concepts, the main advantages and opportunities for practical application by users of new products and technologies of the digital economy, we will consider the features of their use in some sectors of the economy.

2.1. Trading

In retail and wholesale trade, the use of digital sensors, scanners, and other products of the digital economy allow entrepreneurs to manage the inventory of goods and their sale, the formation of e-commerce strategies, pricing and a number of other actions in the network of physical and virtual stores and storages in real time and in a semi-autonomous mode. It seems obvious that over time, the bulk of interactions between people in this area will be shifted exclusively to products of the digital economy, for example, such as servers, switches, routers, Internet network resources and other telecommunications devices capable of storing and processing large amounts of information practically without human participation [3].

The retail sector is undergoing a significant transformation, thanks to the impact of social networks. In modern conditions, they have become one of the most important and significant products of the digital economy, access to which is characterized by the greatest simplicity and clarity. For companies and enterprises, the advantages of participating in social networks are to provide the necessary information about the goods produced and the services rendered to the widest segments of the population who can become potential consumers of products. The advantages of participating in social networks ensure receiving feedback from customers, acquiring new customers, increasing sales and generating additional profit. Consumers of new products and technologies of the digital economy benefit from greater visibility of goods and prices in real time. New convenience and opportunities for transactional purchases contribute to the growth of competition and the well-being of users of digital economy products [4].

2.2. Logistics

Logistics is closely connected with the trade sector of the economy. Many experts believed that digital processing of information about the storage, formation of batches of goods

and their delivery for subsequent sale would be able to replace a sufficiently large number of operators-individuals engaged in this industry. Indeed, with the introduction of digital economy products into logistics, it was possible to significantly increase the volume of goods' delivery. About 85 million shipments of goods are delivered around the world every day [5]. However, so far it has not been possible to achieve a significant increase in efficiency in this industry, since, despite the measures taken to optimize the loading of transport, up to 50% of trucks remain unloaded on the way back after the delivery of a batch of goods.

To increase efficiency in logistics, many enterprises are actively creating platforms with digital support that decentralize the monitoring and control of the delivery of batches of goods. Information and analytical services based on the simultaneous use of cloud computing and computer analytics, position data in the logistics centers of the business. All this information is aimed at identifying problems and optimizing the decisions made. A wide range of information services allows to significantly reduce all types of operating costs and ensures an increase in the efficiency of logistics operations. The emergence of new means of delivery, for example, unmanned aerial vehicles, will open up new opportunities for improving the efficiency of logistics for the delivery of goods [5].

2.3. Automobile industry

In the production of cars in recent years, many enterprises have successfully implemented a strategy of decentralizing production processes to reduce their costs and potential risks. It is based on the model of assembly of innovation reproduction chains. It can be described "as a complex structure aimed at timely receipt of all components, aggregates and other parts of cars for their assembly at production facilities in the allotted time intervals [6]. Wireless mobile communications, cloud computing analytics and technologies for processing large amounts of information increase the efficiency of using the model of assembling innovation reproduction chains in the automotive industry by increasing the transparency of relationships between all manufacturers and timely data analysis. Their use allows to reduce the time of assembly of cars. Most of the integration of digital economy products into the models of assembly of innovation reproduction chains is carried out through cloud computing. This allows you to quickly analyze the results obtained throughout the entire chain in order to increase its efficiency.

2.4. Labor market

The digital economy and its products have a direct influence on labor markets. It is expressed in the fact that as a result of increasing demand for labor with narrow or specific skills, some professions will bring specialists significantly higher wages. In addition, new professions are expected to appear, which will complement the emergence of innovative technologies for the production of goods and the provision of services. At the same time, some professions will lose their relevance and disappear as a result of digitalization.

There is a wide range of professions that can be affected by automation [7]. The most susceptible professions for automation are related to the transport and logistics industries, office and administrative services, the production of standard components for the assembly of obsolete equipment, electronic sales and services that do not require specialists to have a high level of social skills or the ability to solve routine tasks. The professions that are least susceptible to automation are focused on the development of creative and social skills, the ability to persuade, negotiate, and the ability to master original or mutually complementary technologies. Creative professions include most jobs in the fields of education, healthcare, management, business, finance, sports and art, science and technology.

Technological changes in the distribution of employment by profession are not new, but they may become more urgent and widespread in the near future from a year to 3-5 years. Thus, in the USA, Europe and Canada, since the 70s of the last century, there has been an increase in the share of employment in both high and low-skilled jobs [8]. In particular, the share of employment increased for highly qualified specialists in the fields of management and technical professions, and the share of employment for low-skilled specialists increased in the field of sales and service. At the same time, since the 1990s, the share of employment has decreased for mid-level specialists in the production sector and the administrative services support sector. These trends have contributed to the polarization of the US labor market. The experience of Canada was about the same. However, after 2000, professions related to the development of the digital economy began to dominate in Canada [8]. This fact indicates that changes in the technological development of the economy are becoming more important in determining the results of professional employment of the population of Canada. In our case, this applies to any other country engaged in the development of the digital economy.

Opinion

The performed research allowed to formulate following opinions.

The digital economy has a significant influence on the social perceptions of users about its products in almost all spheres and branches of production activity. Today, more and more business tasks that were previously performed manually have already been transferred to various products of the digital economy. Naturally, many of these processes occur in digital form through "communication" between several servers, communication nodes and information processing. They update information upon receipt of goods, check its completeness, process requests for its delivery to potential users, and, ultimately, connect digital information processing with processes and people in the real sector of the economy.

The social perceptions of users about the products of the digital economy are most noticeable in high-tech enterprises with a high level of human capital and intensive use of knowledge. However, an increase in productivity across the entire economy of an individual

country may not occur until the "deployment phase" of new technologies and business processes is reached, as well as until there is an urgent need to use the products of the digital economy in most spheres and sectors of life.

Today, the world community forms the principles of the digital economy functioning. For the real success of this process, it is necessary to adapt the economy of each country to the positive social ideas of users about the products of the digital economy, to ensure the flexibility of their perception not only by individual enterprises, but also by the market as a whole. At the same time, the economic benefits of using the products of the digital economy should be clear at all levels, from an ordinary employee to a production manager.

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